

PHYSICAL FITNESS OF BADMINTON PLAYERS AT DIFFERENT AGE PERIODS

¹Abdikarimov Murad Abdulayevich

TerDPI theory of physical education and sports training and 2nd stage master's student in the field of methodology

Email:abdikarimovmurod6@gmail.com

²Khurramov Urol Khushbak's son

TerDPI theory of physical education and sports training and 2nd stage master's student in the field of methodology

Email:urolxurramov577@gmail.com

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7874811>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th April 2023

Accepted: 27th April 2023

Online: 28th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Technical-tactical training, pedagogical influence, agility, flexibility, agility, fast, youth periods, preparation.

ABSTRACT

This article states that it is important to improve the physical fitness of badminton players at different ages and that it plays an important role in the physiology, physical and mental health of children.

It is known that the training process started at an early age should be focused on the development of the athlete's organism, therefore, the pattern of strength and potential that determines the nature of physical development should be the main factor in training programs.

At the age of 13-16, the rapid development of basic qualities and the emergence of basic techniques take place. Therefore, in the training of a badminton player, to teach badminton, it is necessary to pay attention to technical tactical movements, complex offensive movements, types of technical movements, combinations of movements. In the technical and tactical training of badminton players of this age, it is necessary to identify special features for further development. At the final stage of this stage, badminton players can be divided into such categories as strong players and fast athletes.

From the age of 16, the quality of competition increases. At the age of 18-19, he shows his high level of ability. In this, the athlete's competitive activity is given priority.

In the course of many years of training, it is desirable that the activity of the competition should be conditionally in four stages. The duration of the training phase of the development of badminton players aged 18 and older depends on the characteristics of the players, so there is no limit between the phases. In determining the nature of the model movement in this step system, it is very important to determine at which stage special attention should be paid to the appropriate level of training for the purposeful use of training tools.

In other words, the rational design of the training process consists in combining training goals and tools and methods. This method can also be used in programming the training process after the analysis of the knowledge about the diagnostics of badminton training. In this case, the steps at this stage in the training programs serve as a goal that determines the characteristics of the subordinate order. The main tasks of this stage of initial physical

training are to strengthen health and train young badminton players, master the basics of badminton techniques and other physical exercises, and increase the level of functional fitness based on comprehensive training. In addition, education of hard work and discipline and interest in sports are among these. At the initial stage of physical training, i.e., when teaching methods to 12-13-year-olds, it is necessary to use more instructional methods. During this period, it is necessary to pay attention to education of quickness and agility, because agility creates a basis for successfully mastering complex technical and tactical actions.

Age criteria and physical fitness. The training of highly qualified athletes depends on the effectiveness of the multi-year training system. It can be described as a rationally organized process of teaching, educating and training badminton players of children, adolescents, teenagers and adults, which is carried out on the basis of educational lessons in sports schools. Long-term training for badminton can be successfully implemented only by taking into account the age characteristics of human development, the level of training, the specific characteristics of the chosen sport, the development of physical qualities, the formation of movement skills and skills. In order to correctly structure the long-term training process, it is necessary to follow the path depending on the age limits at which badminton players achieve their best results. Taking these indicators as an example, many experts determined the age limits for badminton players to show the highest results and put them into practice. Badminton is usually divided into three age groups during the long-term training of players.

Those at the first age limit are great successes (18-19 years old).

The second age limit is the age of optimal opportunities (22-26 years) and retention of high results (26-30).

The fact that coaches know the age limits allows for a better systematization of the long-term training process. However, the age of badminton players is not the only factor that must be taken into account in the rational system of long-term training. It is necessary to take into account the most convenient periods for training special physical qualities of badminton, as well as the ability to perform technical and tactical movements in a qualitative manner. During adolescence, there are favorable opportunities for developing physical qualities. In this case, it is necessary to ensure rational and systematic pedagogical influence. Pedagogical influence that develops the physical qualities of young badminton players helps to fully manifest the most obvious physical qualities at one or another stage of youth development.

The main tasks of in-depth physical training are as follows: all-round physical fitness of badminton players, strengthening their health, training general endurance and quick strength qualities, mastering the basics of conducting the competition in a combined method, developing special endurance, obtaining the result of the competition. The main methods of training, the game will be evenly variable and repetitive. Training tools: sports games, cross-country running, special badminton exercises, acrobatic exercises, exercises with small weights, competitive training competitions. It has been proved by many experts that comprehensive training of badminton at the stage of in-depth sports specialization has a great effect.

When planning the badminton training process, it is necessary to devote a lot of time to technical and tactical preparation, because badminton players need to master a large amount of attack movements. During this period, it is necessary to teach the correct biodynamic

structure of technical movement. However, success in technical training in many cases depends on the most favorable proportions of the development of physical qualities of badminton players. should be continued due to the inclusion of special exercises aimed at training physical qualities. During this period, great attention is paid to the development of quick strength qualities of teenage badminton players. At this stage, it is necessary to continue training the flexibility of badminton players. Stretching exercises that help increase the range of motion are an important tool in developing flexibility.

In conclusion, it is necessary to pay special attention to education of endurance during this period of training. Cross-country running, sports games, and swimming sports are included in the training of general endurance. According to V.G. Vadyushin, a great place should be devoted to training agility in sports exercises, i.e. acquiring movement skills and abilities, improving the ability to effectively reconstruct movement activities when the situation changes. That is why training agility involves improving the abilities of mastering coordinated complex movements and reorganizing movement activities in accordance with the suddenly changing situation of badminton players. These recommendations apply to the type of volleyball, during which the athlete's activity takes place in conflict situations with options. The main means of training a badminton player's agility are sports games, acrobatics and gymnastics.

In addition to training, in order to effectively restore the body's performance, in the daily activities of a badminton player, massage, swimming in the pool, steam bath (once a week), and a diet rich in vitamins and oxygen are recommended to achieve the most comfortable schedule of training and rest.

References:

1. A.A Pulatov, O.M. Savatyugen, SH.Sh Isroilov, Badminton nazariyasi va uslubiyoti. TOSHKENT. "Fan va texnologiya" nashriyoti
2. Alisherovich, A. D., & Kizi, K. G. A. (2022). Formation of a Healthy Lifestyle as a Pedagogical Problem in Physical Education Courses of Higher Education Schools. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 209-211.
3. Chorievna, D. Y., & Or'olovich, B. C. (2021). Opportunities to use national and movement games in physical education and athletics. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(05), 909-913.
4. Menglimurod O'g'li, E. E. (2021). Effectiveness and Advantages of using Pedagogical Technologies in Teaching Sports. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(6), 92-94.
5. Urolovich, B. C. (2021). Features of the Methods used in Physical Education. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(6), 88-91.
6. Ulaboyevich, B. G. . (2023). Increasing the Efficiency of the Methodology of Conducting Physical Education Lessons for Students of Grades 5-9 in Hot Climate Conditions. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(4), 137-140.
7. Ulobaevich, B. G. A. (2022). Natural Health Instructions in Organizing the Daily Life of School Students Efficiency of Use Reasonable Use in Physical Education. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 177-179.

8. Tashmurotov, F. (2022). THE DEVELOPMENT OF BADMINTON. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(7), 199-202.
9. Bobokulov, C. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL AND PHYSICAL ASPECTS OF PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(5), 147-149
10. Abduqahhorovich, S. X. . (2023). Strength Training in Football Training. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2(3), 138-141
11. O'ROLOVICH, C. B., & O'GLI, E. E. M. (2020). The Role and Effective Importance of Moving Games in the Development of the Physical Qualities of Athletes. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 7(10), 136-138.
12. Urolovich, B. C., & Panji o'g'li, A. S. (2022). JISMONIY MADANIYAT DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSIYON PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI. World scientific research journal, 4(2), 126-131.
13. Bobokulov, C. (2023). EFFECTIVE USE OF GAMES IN TEACHING SKILLS TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 2(4), 113-116.
14. Tashmurotov, F. (2022). THE DEVELOPMENT OF BADMINTON. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(7), 199-202.
15. Bobokulov Chori Urolovich, Zarina Rakhimova Fakhridin qizi. (2023). CHARACTERISTICS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE FORMATION IN THE FAMILY. IQRO JURNALI, 2(1), 325-330
16. Eshqobilov Elmurod, Bobokulov Chori Urolovich. (2023). FACTORS DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS. IQRO JURNALI, 2(1), 293-297.
17. ESHQOBILOV, E. (2023). SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE COMPETENT APPROACH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY IN THE FUTURE PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF PHYSICAL CULTURE EDUCATION STUDENTS. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(3), 530-533.
18. Tashmurotov, F. (2022). THE DEVELOPMENT OF BADMINTON. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(7), 199-202.
19. Bobokulov Chori Urolovich Eshqobilov Elmurod Menglimurod's Son. (2023). STANDARDS FOR CORRECT ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURE EDUCATION STUDENTS. IQRO JURNALI, 2(1), 319-324.
20. Erikhonovich, T. F. (2022). Method of Organization Lessons of Physical Education in Secondary Schools. European journal of innovation in nonformal education, 2(3), 238-241.
21. ESHQOBILOV ELMUROD MENGLIMUROD O'G'LI. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL CREATIVITY OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENT APPROACH. INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(3), 201-204.
22. Urolovich, B. C. . (2023). Scientific Effects of the Modular Approach in Teaching the Theory and Methodology of Physical Education. Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education, 2(4), 141-144.

23. Alisherovich, O. D. (2022). Improvement of Tactical Training of Boxers. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 53-57.